

Environmental Variables and Power Firms' Productivity: Micro Panel Estimation with Time-Invariant Variables.

Bigerna, S.^a D'Errico, M.C.^{b} Polinori, P.^c*

^{a,b,c} *Department. of Economics (UNIPG)*

^{*} *Corresponding Author*

Key-words: Environmental and Market regulation, Time-Invariant Variables, Bootstrap Malmquist Index, Electricity Sector

JEL-codes: C2 L5 L9 O4 Q4

Introduction

Firms' performance is influenced by both external institutions, such as the stringency of market and environmental regulations, and internal institutions, such as the structure of corporate ownership. This research explores the role of these institutional variables in affecting productivity changes in electricity companies across 15 European countries between 2010 and 2016.

Literature on the effects of market and environmental regulations on power sector provides mixed results (Zhang et al., 2008; Kozluk and Zipperer, 2015; Johnstone et al., 2017; Triebs and Pollitt, 2019). In this study, we aim to enrich the analysis by also considering the interactions with corporate features in affecting firm productivity.

Methods

In a first step, we estimate productivity changes over time using the Bootstrap Malmquist index. Inputs and output data are sourced from the ORBIS database.

In the second step, we estimate the effects of institutional variables using dynamic panel linear models. The external regulatory variables are sourced from the OECD Database, while the internal institutional variables (ownership concentration and public ownership) are sourced from the ORBIS Database. Since internal variables are time-invariant, we employ the procedure proposed by Kripfganz and Schwarz (2019) to consistently identify their effects. This method provides valuable robustness against invalid assumptions regarding the exogeneity of instruments.

Results

Regarding the firm performance, almost all EU countries record a downward trend in the power sector, which reaches its minimum in 2013-2014. After these years, the industrial performance began to recover.

Market regulation has a positive impact on firm performance. Conversely, the stringency of environmental regulation has negative effects.

Regarding internal factors, there is a positive correlation between widespread ownership and firm performance. Moreover, public ownership negatively affects firm performance, supporting the common hypothesis that state-owned utilities optimize an objective function more broadly related to social welfare and energy security, rather than simple profit.

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10052426